

Table of Contents

S1 General	2
S2 Computations	3
Strain energy – method comparison	3
HOMO and LUMO energy levels	5
Bond length alternation (BLA)	6
NICS (nucleus-independent chemical shifts).....	12
Spin density surface - Naphthalene	14
Calculated Energies.....	16
Naphthalene.....	16
Anthracene	18
Tetracene.....	23
References	26

S1 General

All calculations were carried out using the Gaussian 16¹ program applying density functional theory (DFT).² Some calculations were conducted using Møller–Plesset theory. All molecules were optimized using a hybrid density functional and Becke's three-parameter exchange functional combined with the LYP correlation functional (B3LYP) and with the 6-31G(d) basis set.^{3,4} Relaxed scan calculations for naphthalene and anthracene were also optimized using ω B97XD and CAM-B3LYP.⁵

S2 Computations

Strain energy – method comparison

Figure S1. Strain energy of a) bent and b) twisted anthracene calculated at different levels using the 6-31G(d) basis set.

Figure S2. Strain energy of a) bent and b) twisted triplet anthracene calculated at different levels using the 6-31G(d) basis set.

HOMO and LUMO energy levels

Table S1. Change (Δ) in the HOMO and LUMO energy levels and the HOMO–LUMO gap (HLG) upon distorting planar acenes by 30° per ring, calculated using B3LYP/6-31G(d).

	Bent			Twisted		
	Δ HOMO (eV)	Δ LUMO (eV)	Δ HLG (eV)	Δ HOMO (eV)	Δ LUMO (eV)	Δ HLG (eV)
Naphthalene	+0.17	+0.32	+0.14	+0.16	-0.08	-0.24
Anthracene	+0.26	+0.20	-0.06	+0.10	-0.07	-0.17
Tetracene	+0.27	+0.30	+0.03	+0.05	-0.05	-0.10
Pentacene	+0.24	+0.26	+0.02	+0.01	-0.03	-0.04

Figure S3. HOMO and LUMO energy levels for a) bent and b) twisted naphthalene, calculated at different levels using the 6-31G(d) basis set.

Figure S4. Naphthalene HOMO and LUMO orbitals when it has a planar geometry and with a 20° bend or twist calculated at B3LYP/6-31G(d). |isovalue| is 0.02 electrons/bohr³.

Bond length alternation (BLA)

Table S2. Summary of BLA for acenes bent 30° per ring from planarity, calculated with B3LYP/6-31G(d).

Bent Acenes	Singlet		Triplet		Max deviation at 30°/ring T-S (Å)
	Δ BLA (30-0°/ring) in Å	Max. bond deviation at 30°(Å)	Δ BLA (30-0°/ring) in Å	Max. bond deviation at 30°(Å)	
Naphthalene	0.01	0.08 (1.35-1.43)	0.06	0.1 (1.35-1.45)	0.1
Anthracene	0.01	0.08 (1.36-1.44)	0.04	0.07 (1.39-1.46)	0.06
Tetracene	0.01	0.08 (1.37-1.45)	0.01	0.07 (1.39-1.47)	0.05
Pentacene	0.01	0.09 (1.36-1.45)	0.04	0.08 (1.38-1.46)	0.05

Table S3. Summary of BLA for acenes twisted 30° per ring from planarity, calculated with B3LYP/6-31G(d).

Twisted Acenes	Singlet		Triplet		Max deviation at 30°/ring T-S (Å)
	Δ BLA (30-0°/ring) in Å	Max. bond deviation at 30°(Å)	Δ BLA (30-0°/ring) in Å	Max. bond deviation at 30°(Å)	
Naphthalene	0.01	0.05 (1.38-1.43)	0.01	0.09 (1.37-1.46)	0.07
Anthracene	0.01	0.07 (1.38-1.45)	0.01	0.07 (1.40-1.47)	0.05
Tetracene	0.01	0.08 (1.37-1.45)	0.01	0.08 (1.39-1.47)	0.04
Pentacene	0.01	0.09 (1.37-1.46)	0.01	0.08 (1.39-1.47)	0.04

Table S4. Sum of non-zero s coefficients for the HOMO and LUMO orbitals of selected acenes, in their planar, twisted (30° per ring) and bent (30° per ring) conformations, calculated at the RB3LYP/6-31G(d) level.

	HOMO	LUMO
naphthalene-planar	0.00	0.00
naphthalene -twist	0.02	0.10
naphthalene -bent	0.05	0.02
anthracene-planar	0.00	0.00
anthracene -twist	0.02	0.08
anthracene -bent	0.05	0.06
tetracene-planar	0.00	0.00
tetracene -twist	0.02	0.07
tetracene -bent	0.05	0.03
pentacene-planar	0.00	0.00
pentacene-twist	0.03	0.05
pentacene-bent	0.06	0.03

Figure S5. BLA in naphthalene bent (left) or twisted (right) from 0° to 30° per ring as calculated at B3LYP/6-31G(d). Each line represents a different numbered bond whose color is as per the corresponding resonance structure.

Figure S6. BLA in anthracene bent (left) or twisted (right) from 0° to 30° per ring as calculated at B3LYP/6-31G(d). Each line represents a different numbered bond whose color is as per the corresponding resonance structure.

Figure S7. BLA in tetracene bent (left) or twisted (right) from 0° to 30° per ring as calculated at B3LYP/6-31G(d). Each line represents a different numbered bond whose color is as per the corresponding resonance structure.

Figure S8. BLA in pentacene bent (left) or twisted (right) from 0° to 30° per ring as calculated at B3LYP/6-31G(d). Each line represents a different numbered bond whose color is as per the corresponding resonance structure.

NICS (nucleus-independent chemical shifts)

Figure S9. Illustration of NICS(-1), NICS(0) and NICS(1) in anthracene.

Figure S10. NICS calculations for NICS values of -1, 0, and 1 for bent naphthalene from 0° to 30° per ring as calculated at B3LYP/6-31G(d).

Figure S11. NICS calculations for NICS values of -1, 0, and 1 for bent anthracene from 0° to 30° per ring as calculated at B3LYP/6-31G(d).

Figure S12. NICS calculations for NICS values of -1, 0, and 1 for bent tetracene from 0° to 30° per ring as calculated at B3LYP/6-31G(d).

Figure S13. NICS calculations for NICS values of -1, 0, and 1 for bent naphthalene from 0° to 30° per ring as calculated at B3LYP/6-31G(d).

Spin density surface - Naphthalene

Figure S14. Spin density of the triplet state in twisted and bent naphthalene calculated at B3LYP/6-31G(d). A representative resonance structure is presented below each spin density surface. Density [isovalue] is 0.02 electrons/bohr³.

Calculated Energies

Naphthalene

	deg.	Computational method	Energy (Hartree)	Energy (kcal/mol)
planar	0	ub3lyp	-385.8927066	-242148.8311
		ub3lyp-triplet	-385.7928767	-242086.1875
		ucamb3lyp	-385.6594098	-242002.4366
		ump2	-383.3521378	-240554.6165
		uwb97xd	-385.7553629	-242062.6475
twisted	10	ub3lyp	-385.8914484	-242148.0415
		ub3lyp-triplet	-385.7918838	-242085.5645
		ucamb3lyp	-385.6581071	-242001.6192
		ump2	-383.3505444	-240553.6167
		uwb97xd	-385.7540882	-242061.8476
	20	ub3lyp	-385.8876511	-242145.6587
		ub3lyp-triplet	-385.7888747	-242083.6762
		ucamb3lyp	-385.6541756	-241999.1522
		ump2	-383.3458971	-240550.7005
		uwb97xd	-385.7502397	-242059.4327
	30	ub3lyp	-385.8812443	-242141.6384
		ub3lyp-triplet	-385.7837643	-242080.4695
		ucamb3lyp	-385.6475447	-241994.9912
		ump2	-383.338215	-240545.8799
		uwb97xd	-385.7437431	-242055.356
	40	ub3lyp	-385.8721258	-242135.9166
		ub3lyp-triplet	-385.7764239	-242075.8633
		ucamb3lyp	-385.6381094	-241989.0706
		ump2	-383.3273338	-240539.0519
		uwb97xd	-385.734489	-242049.5491
	50	ub3lyp	-385.8601596	-242128.4077
		ub3lyp-triplet	-385.7666927	-242069.757
		ucamb3lyp	-385.6257326	-241981.3041
		ump2	-383.3130496	-240530.0886
		uwb97xd	-385.7223321	-242041.9206
	60	ub3lyp	-385.845205	-242119.0237
		ub3lyp-triplet	-385.7544069	-242062.0476
		ucamb3lyp	-385.6102726	-241971.6029
		ump2	-383.2951791	-240518.8748
		uwb97xd	-385.7071321	-242032.3825
70	ub3lyp	-385.8271263	-242107.6792	
	ub3lyp-triplet	-385.7394053	-242052.634	
	ucamb3lyp	-385.5915934	-241959.8816	
	ump2	-383.2735213	-240505.2844	
	uwb97xd	-385.6887438	-242020.8438	
80	ub3lyp	-385.8057957	-242094.2942	
	ub3lyp-triplet	-385.7215471	-242041.428	

		ucamb3lyp	-385.5695618	-241946.0567
		ump2	-383.2479227	-240489.2212
		uwb97xd	-385.667041	-242007.2252
	90	ub3lyp	-385.7811167	-242078.8081
		ub3lyp-triplet	-385.7081267	-242033.0066
		ucamb3lyp	-385.5440826	-241930.0685
		ump2	-383.2182525	-240470.6031
uwb97xd	-385.6419303	-241991.4682		
bent	0.02	ub3lyp	-385.89	-242147
		ump2	-383.351	-240554
		uwb97xd	-385.754	-242062
		ub3lyp-triplet	-385.781	-242079
		ucamb3lyp	-385.658	-242001
	6.51	ub3lyp	-385.883	-242143
		ub3lyp-triplet	-385.793	-242086
		ucamb3lyp	-385.652	-241998
		ump2	-383.345	-240550
		uwb97xd	-385.747	-242058
	29.96	ub3lyp	-385.878	-242139
		ump2	-383.339	-240546
		uwb97xd	-385.742	-242054
		ub3lyp-triplet	-385.767	-242070
		ucamb3lyp	-385.646	-241994
	32.82	ub3lyp	-385.872	-242136
		ump2	-383.333	-240542
		uwb97xd	-385.737	-242051
		ub3lyp-triplet	-385.762	-242067
		ucamb3lyp	-385.641	-241991
	44.95	ub3lyp	-385.862	-242130
		ump2	-383.321	-240535
		uwb97xd	-385.727	-242045
		ub3lyp-triplet	-385.753	-242061
		ucamb3lyp	-385.631	-241984
	49	ub3lyp	-385.858	-242127
		ump2	-383.317	-240532
		uwb97xd	-385.723	-242042
		ub3lyp-triplet	-385.749	-242058
		ucamb3lyp	-385.627	-241982
	54.49	ub3lyp	-385.852	-242123
		ump2	-383.31	-240528
		uwb97xd	-385.717	-242038
		ub3lyp-triplet	-385.743	-242055
		ucamb3lyp	-385.621	-241978
	62.61	ub3lyp	-385.842	-242117
		ump2	-383.298	-240521
		uwb97xd	-385.707	-242032
		ub3lyp-triplet	-385.733	-242049
		ucamb3lyp	-385.61	-241972

	69.88	ub3lyp	-385.832	-242111
		ump2	-383.286	-240513
		uwb97xd	-385.697	-242026
		ub3lyp-triplet	-385.736	-242051
		ucamb3lyp	-385.6	-241965
	76.53	ub3lyp	-385.822	-242104
		ump2	-383.275	-240506
		uwb97xd	-385.687	-242020
		ub3lyp-triplet	-385.73	-242047
		ucamb3lyp	-385.59	-241959
	82.68	ub3lyp	-385.811	-242098
		ump2	-383.263	-240498
		uwb97xd	-385.677	-242013
		ub3lyp-triplet	-385.723	-242042
		ucamb3lyp	-385.579	-241952
	88.49	ub3lyp	-385.801	-242091
		ump2	-383.251	-240491
		uwb97xd	-385.666	-242007
		ub3lyp-triplet	-385.717	-242038
		ucamb3lyp	-385.569	-241946
94	ub3lyp	-385.791	-242085	
	ump2	-383.239	-240484	
	uwb97xd	-385.656	-242000	
	ub3lyp-triplet	-385.71	-242034	
	ucamb3lyp	-385.558	-241939	

Anthracene

	deg.	Computational method	Energy (Hartree)	Energy (kcal/mol)
planar	0	ub3lyp	-539.5304857	-338556.9984
		ub3lyp-triplet	-539.4639148	-338515.2249
		ucamb3lyp	-539.2072409	-338354.1613
		ucamb3lyp-triplet	-539.1385659	-338311.0675
		ump2	-535.9938271	-336337.7345
		ump2-triplet	-535.9455611	-336307.4474
		uwb97xd	-539.3393119	-338437.0362
		uwb97xd-triplet	-539.2692288	-338393.0589
twisted	10	ub3lyp	-539.5296938	-338556.5014
		ub3lyp-triplet	-539.4632244	-338514.7917
		ucamb3lyp	-539.2064194	-338353.6458
		ucamb3lyp-triplet	-539.1378538	-338310.6207
		ump2	-535.9926119	-336336.9719
		uwb97xd	-539.3385088	-338436.5323
		uwb97xd-triplet	-539.2685349	-338392.6235
	20	ub3lyp	-539.5273119	-338555.0068
		ub3lyp-triplet	-539.4611442	-338513.4864

		ucamb3lyp	-539.2039485	-338352.0953
		ucamb3lyp-triplet	-539.135709	-338309.2748
		ump2	-535.9895887	-336335.0749
		uwb97xd	-539.3360971	-338435.0189
		uwb97xd-triplet	-539.2664432	-338391.3109
	30	ub3lyp	-539.523322	-338552.5031
		ub3lyp-triplet	-539.4576484	-338511.2927
		ucamb3lyp	-539.199809	-338349.4977
		ucamb3lyp-triplet	-539.1321068	-338307.0144
		ump2	-535.9848146	-336332.0791
		uwb97xd	-539.3320561	-338432.4832
		uwb97xd-triplet	-539.2629308	-338389.1069
	40	ub3lyp	-539.5176903	-338548.9692
		ub3lyp-triplet	-539.4526943	-338508.184
		ucamb3lyp	-539.1939675	-338345.8322
		ucamb3lyp-triplet	-539.1270081	-338303.815
		ump2	-535.9781677	-336327.9082
		uwb97xd	-539.3263462	-338428.9002
		uwb97xd-triplet	-539.2579554	-338385.9848
	50	ub3lyp	-539.5103757	-338544.3793
		ub3lyp-triplet	-539.4462322	-338504.129
		ucamb3lyp	-539.1863875	-338341.0757
		ucamb3lyp-triplet	-539.1203663	-338299.6472
		ump2	-535.9695183	-336322.4806
		uwb97xd	-539.3189244	-338424.243
		uwb97xd-triplet	-539.2514672	-338381.9134
	60	ub3lyp	-539.5013407	-338538.7098
		ub3lyp-triplet	-539.4382089	-338499.0944
		ucamb3lyp	-539.1770222	-338335.199
		ucamb3lyp-triplet	-539.1121305	-338294.4792
ump2		-535.9588008	-336315.7554	
uwb97xd		-539.3097505	-338418.4864	
uwb97xd-triplet		-539.2434085	-338376.8566	
70	ub3lyp	-539.4905377	-338531.9309	
	ub3lyp-triplet	-539.428557	-338493.0378	
	ucamb3lyp	-539.1658291	-338328.1753	
	ucamb3lyp-triplet	-539.1022399	-338288.2728	
	ump2	-535.9459803	-336307.7105	
	uwb97xd	-539.2987742	-338411.5987	
	uwb97xd-triplet	-539.233722	-338370.7783	
80	ub3lyp	-539.4779201	-338524.0133	
	ub3lyp-triplet	-539.4172155	-338485.921	
	ucamb3lyp	-539.1527617	-338319.9754	
	ucamb3lyp-triplet	-539.0906388	-338280.9931	
	ump2	-535.9309483	-336298.2779	
	uwb97xd	-539.2859485	-338403.5505	
	uwb97xd-triplet	-539.2223468	-338363.6403	
90	ub3lyp	-539.4634492	-338514.9328	

		ub3lyp-triplet	-539.4041339	-338477.7122
		ucamb3lyp	-539.1377811	-338310.5751
		ucamb3lyp-triplet	-539.0772816	-338272.6114
		ump2	-535.9136733	-336287.4377
		uwb97xd	-539.2712273	-338394.3129
		uwb97xd-triplet	-539.20923	-338355.4095
bent	128.87	ub3lyp	-539.3785174	-338461.6378
		ub3lyp-triplet	-539.3528537	-338445.5338
		ucamb3lyp	-539.0545998	-338258.3785
		ucamb3lyp-triplet	-539.0324199	-338244.4606
		ump2	-535.8188765	-336227.9525
		ump2-triplet	-535.8421602	-336242.5631
		uwb97xd	-539.1916528	-338344.3797
		uwb97xd-triplet	-539.1682774	-338329.7116
	117.86	ub3lyp	-539.3967765	-338473.0954
		ub3lyp-triplet	-539.3653351	-338453.3659
		ucamb3lyp	-539.0730444	-338269.9526
		ucamb3lyp-triplet	-539.0447818	-338252.2177
		ump2	-535.8402888	-336241.3887
		ump2-triplet	-535.8557421	-336251.0857
		uwb97xd	-539.2092736	-338355.4368
		uwb97xd-triplet	-539.1798266	-338336.9587
	112.34	ub3lyp	-539.408699	-338480.5768
		ub3lyp-triplet	-539.3733176	-338458.3749
		ucamb3lyp	-539.0851145	-338277.5266
		ucamb3lyp-triplet	-539.0526823	-338257.1753
		ump2	-535.8542855	-336250.1717
		ump2-triplet	-535.8642715	-336256.438
		uwb97xd	-539.2208598	-338362.7072
		uwb97xd-triplet	-539.1872515	-338341.6179
	106.14	ub3lyp	-539.4204184	-338487.9308
		ub3lyp-triplet	-539.3810947	-338463.2551
		ucamb3lyp	-539.0969984	-338284.9838
		ucamb3lyp-triplet	-539.0603654	-338261.9965
		ump2	-535.8680395	-336258.8024
		ump2-triplet	-535.872445	-336261.5669
uwb97xd		-539.2323034	-338369.8881	
uwb97xd-triplet		-539.1945012	-338346.1671	
100.72	ub3lyp	-539.4319469	-338495.165	
	ub3lyp-triplet	-539.3887157	-338468.0373	
	ucamb3lyp	-539.1087022	-338292.328	
	ucamb3lyp-triplet	-539.0678692	-338266.7051	
	ump2	-535.8815886	-336267.3045	
	ump2-triplet	-535.8803023	-336266.4973	
	uwb97xd	-539.2435991	-338376.9762	
	uwb97xd-triplet	-539.2016069	-338350.6259	
94.55	ub3lyp	-539.4433109	-338502.2959	
	ub3lyp-triplet	-539.3962196	-338472.746	

		ucamb3lyp	-539.1202365	-338299.5658
		ucamb3lyp-triplet	-539.0752229	-338271.3196
		ump2	-535.8949672	-336275.6996
		ump2-triplet	-535.887874	-336271.2486
		uwb97xd	-539.2547449	-338383.9702
		uwb97xd-triplet	-539.2085909	-338355.0084
	88.07	ub3lyp	-539.4544975	-338509.3155
		ub3lyp-triplet	-539.4036356	-338477.3996
		ucamb3lyp	-539.1315933	-338306.6922
		ucamb3lyp-triplet	-539.0824501	-338275.8547
		ump2	-535.9080943	-336283.9369
		ump2-triplet	-535.895184	-336275.8356
		uwb97xd	-539.2657251	-338390.8603
		uwb97xd-triplet	-539.2154721	-338359.3264
	81.18	ub3lyp	-539.4654991	-338516.2191
		ub3lyp-triplet	-539.4110079	-338482.0257
		ucamb3lyp	-539.1427669	-338313.7037
		ucamb3lyp-triplet	-539.0895856	-338280.3322
		ump2	-535.9210081	-336292.0403
		ump2-triplet	-535.9022556	-336280.2731
		uwb97xd	-539.276536	-338397.6442
		uwb97xd-triplet	-539.222278	-338363.5971
	77.55	ub3lyp	-539.4709358	-338519.6306
		ub3lyp-triplet	-539.4146967	-338484.3404
		ucamb3lyp	-539.1482885	-338317.1685
		ucamb3lyp-triplet	-539.0931328	-338282.5581
		ump2	-535.9273853	-336296.0421
		ump2-triplet	-535.9057062	-336282.4384
		uwb97xd	-539.2818795	-338400.9972
		uwb97xd-triplet	-539.2256645	-338365.7222
	73.78	ub3lyp	-539.4763335	-338523.0177
		ub3lyp-triplet	-539.4183979	-338486.6629
		ucamb3lyp	-539.1537683	-338320.6071
		ucamb3lyp-triplet	-539.0966745	-338284.7805
		ump2	-535.9337064	-336300.0086
		ump2-triplet	-535.9091043	-336284.5707
		uwb97xd	-539.2871829	-338404.3251
		uwb97xd-triplet	-539.2290478	-338367.8452
	69.82	ub3lyp	-539.4816905	-338526.3792
		ub3lyp-triplet	-539.4221192	-338488.9981
		ucamb3lyp	-539.159206	-338324.0192
		ucamb3lyp-triplet	-539.1002169	-338287.0034
		ump2	-535.9399748	-336303.942
		ump2-triplet	-535.9124514	-336286.671
		uwb97xd	-539.2924465	-338407.6281
		uwb97xd-triplet	-539.232433	-338369.9694
	65.66	ub3lyp	-539.4870062	-338529.7149
		ub3lyp-triplet	-539.425868	-338491.3504

		ucamb3lyp	-539.1646006	-338327.4044
		ucamb3lyp-triplet	-539.103767	-338289.2311
		ump2	-535.9461869	-336307.8401
		ump2-triplet	-535.9157521	-336288.7422
		uwb97xd	-539.2976704	-338410.9061
		uwb97xd-triplet	-539.2358258	-338372.0984
	61.28	ub3lyp	-539.4922781	-338533.023
		ub3lyp-triplet	-539.4296521	-338493.725
		ucamb3lyp	-539.1699521	-338330.7625
		ucamb3lyp-triplet	-539.107333	-338291.4688
		ump2	-535.9523446	-336311.7041
		ump2-triplet	-535.9190112	-336290.7873
		uwb97xd	-539.3028542	-338414.1589
		uwb97xd-triplet	-539.2392332	-338374.2366
	56.59	ub3lyp	-539.4975074	-338536.3044
		ub3lyp-triplet	-539.4334805	-338496.1273
		ucamb3lyp	-539.1752615	-338334.0941
		ucamb3lyp-triplet	-539.1109248	-338293.7226
		ump2	-535.9584475	-336315.5337
		ump2-triplet	-535.9222369	-336292.8114
		uwb97xd	-539.3079959	-338417.3854
		uwb97xd-triplet	-539.2426636	-338376.3891
	51.49	ub3lyp	-539.502698	-338539.5615
		ub3lyp-triplet	-539.437363	-338498.5636
		ucamb3lyp	-539.1805315	-338337.4011
		ucamb3lyp-triplet	-539.1145545	-338296.0003
		ump2	-535.9644945	-336319.3282
		ump2-triplet	-535.9254308	-336294.8156
		uwb97xd	-539.3130961	-338420.5857
		uwb97xd-triplet	-539.2461259	-338378.5617
	45.88	ub3lyp	-539.5078522	-338542.7958
		ub3lyp-triplet	-539.4413093	-338501.0399
		ucamb3lyp	-539.1857647	-338340.6849
		ucamb3lyp-triplet	-539.1182355	-338298.3101
		ump2	-535.9704862	-336323.088
		ump2-triplet	-535.9286066	-336296.8084
		uwb97xd	-539.3181564	-338423.7611
		uwb97xd-triplet	-539.2496323	-338380.762
	39.57	ub3lyp	-539.5129732	-338546.0092
		ub3lyp-triplet	-539.4453277	-338503.5615
		ucamb3lyp	-539.190963	-338343.9469
		ucamb3lyp-triplet	-539.1219821	-338300.6611
		ump2	-535.9764235	-336326.8137
		ump2-triplet	-535.9317553	-336298.7842
		uwb97xd	-539.3231837	-338426.9157
		uwb97xd-triplet	-539.2531957	-338382.9981
	32.08	ub3lyp	-539.5180621	-338549.2025
		ub3lyp-triplet	-539.4494218	-338506.1305

		ucamb3lyp	-539.1961284	-338347.1882
		ucamb3lyp-triplet	-539.1258058	-338303.0605
		ump2	-535.9823092	-336330.507
		ump2-triplet	-535.934928	-336300.7751
		uwb97xd	-539.3281781	-338430.0497
		uwb97xd-triplet	-539.2568283	-338385.2775
	22.28	ub3lyp	-539.5231196	-338552.3761
		ub3lyp-triplet	-539.4535899	-338508.746
		ucamb3lyp	-539.201265	-338350.4114
		ucamb3lyp-triplet	-539.1297157	-338305.514
		ump2	-535.9881282	-336334.1584
		ump2-triplet	-535.9381062	-336302.7695
		uwb97xd	-539.3331333	-338433.1591
		uwb97xd-triplet	-539.260535	-338387.6035
	0.12	ub3lyp	-539.5281405	-338555.5267
		ub3lyp-triplet	-539.4578287	-338511.4059
		ucamb3lyp	-539.2060662	-338353.4242
		ucamb3lyp-triplet	-539.133718	-338308.0254
		ump2	-535.9939128	-336337.7883
		ump2-triplet	-535.9412528	-336304.744
		uwb97xd	-539.3379091	-338436.156
		uwb97xd-triplet	-539.2643224	-338389.9801

Tetracene

	deg.	Computational method	Energy (Hartree)	Energy (kcal/mol)
planar	0	ub3lyp	-693.1657575	-434963.5923
		ub3lyp-triplet	-693.1216124	-434935.8911
twisted	10	ub3lyp	-693.1651887	-434963.2354
		ub3lyp-triplet	-693.1210914	-434935.5642
	20	ub3lyp	-693.1634747	-434962.1599
		ub3lyp-triplet	-693.1195246	-434934.581
	30	ub3lyp	-693.1606105	-434960.3626
		ub3lyp-triplet	-693.1168999	-434932.934
	40	ub3lyp	-693.156579	-434957.8328
		ub3lyp-triplet	-693.1131994	-434930.612
	50	ub3lyp	-693.1513657	-434954.5614
		ub3lyp-triplet	-693.1083994	-434927.5999
	60	ub3lyp	-693.1449599	-434950.5418
		ub3lyp-triplet	-693.1024809	-434923.8861
	70	ub3lyp	-693.1373375	-434945.7587
		ub3lyp-triplet	-693.095406	-434919.4466
	80	ub3lyp	-693.1284772	-434940.1988
		ub3lyp-triplet	-693.0871471	-434914.2641
	90	ub3lyp	-693.1183642	-434933.8529

	100	ub3lyp-triplet	-693.0776792	-434908.3229
		ub3lyp	-693.1069817	-434926.7103
	110	ub3lyp-triplet	-693.0669771	-434901.6073
		ub3lyp	-693.0943149	-434918.7619
	120	ub3lyp-triplet	-693.0550185	-434894.1033
		ub3lyp	-693.0803486	-434909.998
bent	115.46	ub3lyp	-693.055352	-434894.3125
		ub3lyp-triplet	-693.016596	-434869.993
	108.01	ub3lyp	-693.0690622	-434902.9157
		ub3lyp-triplet	-693.0291637	-434877.8793
	100.22	ub3lyp	-693.0823928	-434911.2807
		ub3lyp-triplet	-693.0414477	-434885.5876
	92	ub3lyp	-693.0953684	-434919.423
		ub3lyp-triplet	-693.0534468	-434893.117
	83.2	ub3lyp	-693.1080154	-434927.359
		ub3lyp-triplet	-693.0652001	-434900.4923
	73.61	ub3lyp	-693.1203469	-434935.097
		ub3lyp-triplet	-693.0767174	-434907.7194
	71.99	ub3lyp	-693.1222831	-434936.312
		ub3lyp-triplet	-693.0785309	-434908.8574
	62.84	ub3lyp	-693.1323659	-434942.639
		ub3lyp-triplet	-693.0879972	-434914.7975
	50.15	ub3lyp	-693.1441146	-434950.0113
		ub3lyp-triplet	-693.0990792	-434921.7515
	33.29	ub3lyp	-693.1556011	-434957.2192
		ub3lyp-triplet	-693.1099635	-434928.5814

Pentacene

	deg.	Computational method	Energy (Hartree)	Energy (kcal/mol)
planar	0	ub3lyp	-846.7998742	-531369.4615
		ub3lyp-triplet	-846.7713893	-531351.5871
twisted	10	ub3lyp	-846.7994306	-531369.1831
		ub3lyp-triplet	-846.7709717	-531351.3251
	20	ub3lyp	-846.7980965	-531368.3459
		ub3lyp-triplet	-846.7697179	-531350.5383
	30	ub3lyp	-846.7958697	-531366.9486
		ub3lyp-triplet	-846.7676211	-531349.2225
	40	ub3lyp	-846.7927392	-531364.9842
		ub3lyp-triplet	-846.7646689	-531347.37
	50	ub3lyp	-846.7887007	-531362.4501
		ub3lyp-triplet	-846.7608552	-531344.9769
	60	ub3lyp	-846.78375	-531359.3435
		ub3lyp-triplet	-846.7561678	-531342.0356

	70	ub3lyp	-846.7778691	-531355.6532	
		ub3lyp-triplet	-846.7505859	-531338.5329	
	80	ub3lyp	-846.7710509	-531351.3748	
		ub3lyp-triplet	-846.7440957	-531334.4603	
	90	ub3lyp	-846.7632909	-531346.5053	
		ub3lyp-triplet	-846.7366891	-531329.8126	
	100	ub3lyp	-846.7545817	-531341.0403	
		ub3lyp-triplet	-846.7283492	-531324.5793	
	110	ub3lyp	-846.7449138	-531334.9736	
		ub3lyp-triplet	-846.719058	-531318.7491	
	120	ub3lyp	-846.7342789	-531328.3002	
		ub3lyp-triplet	-846.7088014	-531312.313	
	130	ub3lyp	-846.7226691	-531321.015	
		ub3lyp-triplet	-846.6975675	-531305.2637	
	140	ub3lyp	-846.7100736	-531313.1113	
		ub3lyp-triplet	-846.6853434	-531297.593	
	150	ub3lyp	-846.6964797	-531304.5811	
		ub3lyp-triplet	-846.6721123	-531289.2905	
	bent	131.53	ub3lyp	-846.6771613	-531292.4587
			ub3lyp-triplet	-846.6569688	-531279.7879
126.32		ub3lyp	-846.686698	-531298.4431	
		ub3lyp-triplet	-846.6648685	-531284.745	
122.21		ub3lyp	-846.6960052	-531304.2834	
		ub3lyp-triplet	-846.6727763	-531289.7071	
115.57		ub3lyp	-846.7050906	-531309.9845	
		ub3lyp-triplet	-846.680717	-531294.69	
110.01		ub3lyp	-846.7139607	-531315.5505	
		ub3lyp-triplet	-846.6886792	-531299.6863	
104.27		ub3lyp	-846.7226351	-531320.9937	
		ub3lyp-triplet	-846.696628	-531304.6742	
98.33		ub3lyp	-846.7311267	-531326.3222	
		ub3lyp-triplet	-846.7045258	-531309.6301	
92.15		ub3lyp	-846.7394486	-531331.5442	
		ub3lyp-triplet	-846.7123391	-531314.5329	
85.65		ub3lyp	-846.7475867	-531336.6509	
		ub3lyp-triplet	-846.7200403	-531319.3654	
78.78		ub3lyp	-846.7555604	-531341.6544	
		ub3lyp-triplet	-846.7276291	-531324.1274	
74.88	ub3lyp	-846.7597803	-531344.3024		
	ub3lyp-triplet	-846.731658	-531326.6556		
71.38	ub3lyp	-846.7633847	-531346.5642		
	ub3lyp-triplet	-846.7351063	-531328.8194		
63.3	ub3lyp	-846.7710492	-531351.3737		
	ub3lyp-triplet	-846.7424611	-531333.4346		
54.21	ub3lyp	-846.7785825	-531356.1009		
	ub3lyp-triplet	-846.7497147	-531337.9862		
43.46	ub3lyp	-846.7859839	-531360.7453		
	ub3lyp-triplet	-846.7568607	-531342.4704		

	29.3	ub3lyp	-846.7932606	-531365.3114
		ub3lyp-triplet	-846.7639016	-531346.8885

References

- [1] Gaussian 09, Revision A.02, M. J. Frisch, G. W. Trucks, H. B. Schlegel, G. E. Scuseria, M. A. Robb, J. R. Cheeseman, G. Scalmani, V. Barone, G. A. Petersson, H. Nakatsuji, X. Li, M. Caricato, A. Marenich, J. Bloino, B. G. Janesko, R. Gomperts, B. Mennucci, H. P. Hratchian, J. V. Ortiz, A. F. Izmaylov, J. L. Sonnenberg, D. Williams-Young, F. Ding, F. Lipparini, F. Egidi, J. Goings, B. Peng, A. Petrone, T. Henderson, D. Ranasinghe, V. G. Zakrzewski, J. Gao, N. Rega, G. Zheng, W. Liang, M. Hada, M. Ehara, K. Toyota, R. Fukuda, J. Hasegawa, M. Ishida, T. Nakajima, Y. Honda, O. Kitao, H. Nakai, T. Vreven, K. Throssell, J. A. Montgomery, Jr., J. E. Peralta, F. Ogliaro, M. Bearpark, J. J. Heyd, E. Brothers, K. N. Kudin, V. N. Staroverov, T. Keith, R. Kobayashi, J. Normand, K. Raghavachari, A. Rendell, J. C. Burant, S. S. Iyengar, J. Tomasi, M. Cossi, J. M. Millam, M. Klene, C. Adamo, R. Cammi, J. W. Ochterski, R. L. Martin, K. Morokuma, O. Farkas, J. B. Foresman, D. J. Fox, Gaussian, Inc., Wallingford CT, **2016**.
- [2] Calais, J.-L., Density-functional theory of atoms and molecules. R.G. Parr, W. Yang, Oxford University Press, New York, Oxford, 1989. IX + 333 pp. *Int. J. Quantum Chem.* **1993**, *47*, 101-101.
- [3] Becke, A. D., Density-functional thermochemistry. III. The role of exact exchange. *J. Chem. Phys.* **1993**, *98*, 5648-5652.
- [4] Lee, C.; Yang, W.; Parr, R. G., Development of the Colle-Salvetti correlation-energy formula into a functional of the electron density. *Phys. Rev. B* **1988**, *37*, 785-789.
- [5] Chai, J.-D.; Head-Gordon, M., Long-range corrected hybrid density functionals with damped atom–atom dispersion corrections. *Phys. Chem. Chem. Phys.* **2008**, *10*, 6615-6620.